

Antibacterial Activity of Compound Isolated from *Calatropis Gigantea* L. Flower against four Important Bacteria in Public Health

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Running head: *Calatropis gigantea* isolates against Bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. mutans*, *B. cereus* & *S. puteda*)

Abstract:

The increased incidence of severe opportunistic bacterial infections is an important problem. In the current study, A phytochemicals study on the flower of *calatropis gigantea linn* by using silica gel column chromatography and thin layer chromatography, isolated the three compound (Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid Palmitoleic acid Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid (compound 1), Oxadiazon (Compound 2) and unknown (Compound 3)). The structural compounds were confirmed by using mass spectroscopy. The confirmed compounds were evaluated in the range of 267.10, 340.20 and 289.10 m/e and the TLC Rf value calculate at 0.1, 0.6 and 0.7 c.m. The antibacterial activity of isolated compound of *calatropis gigantea* was examined against four species of pathogenic and nonpathogenic microorganism: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Pseudomonas puteda* were measured by the disk diffusion method. More specifically, *staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans* represented higher susceptibility at 1000 µg/ml (24±0.30 and 18±0.25) respectively. The Mass Spectrum of activity observed in the present study could be a possible source to obtain new and effective herbal medicines to treat infections, hence justified the ethnic uses of *Calatropis gigantea linn* against various infectious diseases.

Keywords: *Calatropis gigantea* flower extract; Bioactive compound; Mass spectroscopy; Anti-microbial activity

1. Introduction

In current scenario of pharmaceutical and medical field advancement, we have just seen that microbes alter their metabolism and genetic structure to acquire resistant against the drugs used in the treatment of common infectious disease [1, 2]. These drug resistant candidates are the great global fight in the pharmaceutical and healthcare industry. In order to overcome drug resistant, scientists look forward to developing alternative and novel drugs [3]. Natural medicinal sources like animals, plants, and algae provide natural compounds for the treatment of many diseases or illnesses [4]. In recent time, medicinal plants are being extensively researched for refusing medicinal properties. Various researchers have been reported in our studies that the plants are one of the major sources for drug discovery and development [5]. In this study, I was evaluated antibacterial activity to resist bacterial infection. Bacteria are the prokaryotic single celled microorganisms present around us [6]. There are many sizes and shape. The current actual average size of bacteria is about 10^5 meter or 0.2-2.0 micrometer in diameter [7]. Many morphological study shows that most of the bacteria are classified in three basic shapes including spherical, spiral, and rod shape [8]. All type of bacteria are not causing disease some bacteria are good for you, which help in your digestive system for breakdown of food, other bacteria live on your skin, in your lung for oxygen supply and also involve in other part of our body for health [9, 10, 11]. Some bacteria are not good for your body which causes the disease like pneumonia, meningitis, tuberculosis, cholera and other infections [12]. Since, nearly all bacteria are important for living life as they possess enzyme and gene essential in order to survive plant or animals [13]. It is analyzed that about 5×10^{30} bacteria found in the world [14]. However, there are different types of bacteria that can cause diseases in our body. cellulitis is a minor skin infection caused by staphylococcus and mild throat is a good example of streptococcus bacterial infection this are the most common types of bacterial infection [15, 16]. Bacteria used in the food industry for the production of milk. There significant interest on industrial biotechnology as an enzyme, biorefining, biofuels and other pharmaceutical production [9, 17, 18]. Organic and some inorganic compound are essential to bacterial growth or replication including Carbone, Oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, potassium, magnesium and require very small amount of other elements. These substances are used to make the culture media that required for the growth, support and survival of microorganism. Culture media involving energy source, solid media, growth promoting factor, buffer salt and minerals. The assessment of antimicrobial activity various methods used including Turbidometric method, Agar streak dilution method, Serial dilution method, Agar diffusion method [19, 20]. There are several synthetic and semi synthetic agent used for the effective treatment of bacterial infection including Aminoglycoside, Sulfonamide, Quinolones, Chloramphenicol, Macrolides, Tetracycline and Beta Lactam Antibiotics. Many focus on medicinal plant or isolated compound including alkaloid, glycoside, flavonoid, diterpines, sesquiterpine and triterpines that possess antimicrobial effect [21] but their separation is very difficult and major challenge for the process of characterization and identification of active constituents in pharmaceutical industries [22]. The plant

Calatropis gigantea belonging to the family Apocynaceae is a wasteland weed, habitat of Asian and commonly known as milkweed [23]. Long before the ancient peoples utilize the plant parts to cure several illnesses such as toothache, earache, sprain, anxiety, pain, epilepsy, diarrhea and mental disorders [24]. This plant is also scientifically researched for its cytotoxic activity, antipyretic activity, *anti-candida* activity, and wound healing activity [25, 26]. Current study was focused to isolate bioactive compound from crude flower extract of *C. gigantea* and in vitro characterization of isolated compound. The significant steps including for evaluation of Pharmacological active constituents from the medicinal plant are extraction, isolation, characterization, and toxicological evaluation. The following major steps in extraction, isolation and characterization of bioactive compound from plants extract can be show in Figure 1 [27].

Fig.1. A flow chart summarized extraction, isolation and characterization of bioactive compound from plants extract.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant Collection

The Plant selection and collection is mostly important process for making efficient phyto constituent isolation. The disease free and healthy plants only selected for the plant extraction which is protected from weeds and insect. NRCS (Natural resources conservation service) is a plant materials program which created the guidelines how to collect the material, which includes the collection and characterization of flower [28]. Fresh, white or lavender flower of the plant were identified and collected from *Calatropis gigantea*, Gariyaband, Chhattisgarh, India (3 December 2019 at morning time). The confirmation (Authentication) of plant flower was done by Shri N.P.A. Govt. Ayurvedic College, G.E. Road, Aamanaka, Raipur, Chhattisgarh 492001 Raipur (C.G.). The dried flowers were later crushed to obtain a coarse powder for easy extraction using soxlet apparatus.

2.2. Pre- extraction preparation of plant samples

Prior to extraction the bimolecular of plant sample are preserved in dark place. The flower can be extraction form fresh or dried plant material. The powdered flowers (250 g) were defatting with petroleum ether (60°C–80°C) for 48 h. Other pre-preparation of plant material such as comminuting and drying also factor which influence the preservation of phytochemical in the final [29].

2.3. Grinded vs, powder sample

When particle size decrease then surface area is increases so that the contact between sample and solvent also increased, size reduction in which material are reduced to course or fine powders due to large number of surface area contact with extraction solvents. This particular pre- preparation is essential for efficient extraction. This particle size is mentioned in sulaiman et al preparing the plant samples that was grinded to 400 μm (o.4mm) in size commonly mixer electric blender was used for the reduction of powder [30].

2.4. Preparation of methanolic extraction

Soxhlet extraction - Exactly 250 grams of crushed white or lavender flowers of *calatropis gigantea* were extracted with 500 ml of Methanol in an automated Soxhlet apparatus (SOXTEC- ASGI). The crushed plant material or crude drug is placed on the thimble when placed between the round bottom and condenser and inside the chamber filter paper are placed. The side arm is tagged with cotton wool the solvent Methanol heated through heating mental and its vapor is moving through or condensate in condenser. The condensed drips-condensed into the thimble containing crude drug when the level of solvent in the chamber reaches the siphon tube, the active constituent of the chamber is porous back on round bottom flask and the cycle is repeated again. The active constituent remained in the round bottom flask when cycle is repeated. The process of filling and emptying is run for a total of 16 hours at 60°C. The equipment can be turned on and off when the process is not performed. When the process has finished, the Methanol should be evaporated by using Rota evaporator and then freeze dried (-20°C) to obtain solid residue. The plant material leaving from round bottom flask and keep at 40°C in air tight sterile vials in the refrigerator. The extraction percentage was calculated by the following formula [31, 32].

$$\% \text{ Extraction} = \frac{\text{Weight of the extract (g)}}{\text{Weight of the plant material (g)}} \times 100$$

2.5. Isolation and purification of bioactive compounds from plant samples

2.5.1. Test sample

Methanol extract was dried by using rotary evaporator (depending on the nature of the work) before loading into silica gel column (60-120 mesh). 10 g of the sample were taken in order to define the yield

of desired extract. The solvent system for column chromatography was using on the basis of separation achieved by TLC.

2.5.2. Gradient solvent system

Gradient solvent system (non-polar to high polar solvent system) obtained best result as well as obtained best separation for various bioactive compounds from any medicinal plant extract. Two solvent systems mainly used as more than solvent which cause change in the temperature of solvent and the separation of compound become altered. However, the volume of solvent can be dependent on the amount of the sample to be separated. In this way, the separation of compounds from the mixture of different compounds was achieved. The individual compounds were collected as fractions and analyzed further for structure elucidation [33].

2.6. Identification of major compound

2.6.1. Column-chromatography

The stationary phase (silica gel) (# 60-120) is stow slowly as an adsorbent in cylinder shaped glass column with a liquid solvent that flows down the column with the help of gravitational force. The compounds in mixture have different interactions ability with stationary phase (silica gel), however, the polar compound separated first as compare to non-polar compounds. This technique is used for the purification of compounds from a mixture [34].

2.6.2. Isolation of phyto constituents from *Calatropis gigantea* flower

Fractionates of Methanolic extract was done by column Chromatography. In the first step column was eluted with Methanol and dichloromethane combinations in the ratio (1:9, 2:8, 3:6, 9:1) (Table 1.1.) and 4 fractions of 100 ml each were collected. The fractions collected were concentrated by using rotary evaporator. The individual fraction was spotted in TLC plate at 2mm above from the solvent using ethyl acetate and hexane (2:8) as a mobile phase and as a result number of spot was obtained in fraction 1 (Figure 1 (A)). In the second step; fraction 1 was show better separation of the visible spots. However, this fraction was concentrated by using rotary evaporator, after that they was loaded in column and eluted with 100% hexane in increased the polarity produced ethyl acetate in the ratio summarized (8: 92, 10:90, 15: 75, 15:35, 20:30, 25:25, 30:20, 35:15, 40:10, 45:5, 50:50) (Table1.2). 11 fractions were collected and TLC was performed. The Three spots in the F6 and F'5 fraction were obtained (Figure 1 (B)). I had selected Fraction-6 was rechromatographed on silica gel eluting with 100% methanol and through the uv chamber its R_f value was determined as 0.1, 0.6 and 0.7, in ethyl acetate: Hexane (2:8) in (Table 2). The compound was labeled as F6. The isolated compound characterized by mass spectroscopy. The fractions F6 were kept in a fume hood to dry. Yellowish amorphous solids were obtained from the fraction F6. The solids were washed with dichloromethane, dissolved in methanol and checked for purity and the developed TLC plate was then viewed in an iodine chamber. Three spot were detected. The solvent was

evaporated to dryness and kept for 24 h. A whitish crystal was precipitated out at the bottom of the test tube. It was recrystallized from methanol as white needles (1.62 mg, 0.060% of dried chloroform extract).

Fig. 2. Thin layer chromatography of methanolic extract of *calatropis gigantea* flower in different solvent system for (A) Methanol: Dichloromethane fractions in the different ratio (1:9, 2:8, 3:6, 9:1) were spotted in each plate in which only fraction 1 was eluted better separation as compared to the other 3 fractions. (B) In case of Hexane: Ethyl Acetate fraction F6 & F'5 showed better separation and three spot were eluted.

Table 1. Summarizes the ratio of solvent to be used in column chromatography.

Gradient solvent system to be used in the column-chromatography for the isolation of bioactive molecules from any test samples			
Solvent system	Ratio	Volume (ml)	Fraction
Methanol : Dichloromethane	10:90	100	1
Methanol : Dichloromethane	20:80	100	2
Methanol : Dichloromethane	30:60	100	3
Methanol : Dichloromethane	90:10	100	4

Table 2. Summarizes the ratio of solvent to be used in column chromatography.

Gradient solvent system to be used in the column-chromatography for the isolation of bioactive molecules from any test samples			
Solvent system	Ratio	Volume (mL)	Fraction
Hexane	100%		
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	8:92	50	F1
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	10:90	50	F2
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	15:75	50	F3
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	15:35	50	F4
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	20:30	50	F5
Ethyl acetate: Hexane	25:25	50	F6
Ethyl acetate	50%		
Hexane: Ethyl acetate	30:20	50	F'1
Hexane: Ethyl acetate	35:15	50	F'2
Hexane: Ethyl acetate	40:10	50	F'3

Hexane: Ethyl acetate	45:05	50	F'4
Hexane: Ethyl acetate	50:50	50	F'5

2.6.4. Application and development of TLC plate for identification of compound

Prepared the solvent system and poured it into the chamber and saturated the chamber by lining the chamber with a piece of filter paper that has been wet with the mobile phase. The solvent system used for detecting compounds in extract of *calatropis gigantea* was hexane: ethyl acetate (2:8), and the spraying reagent used was dragendroff's reagent. The number of spots was identified and Rf value calculated.

2.6.5. Calculation of Rf value

The Rf value (Table 3) of the spots were calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Rf Value} = \frac{\text{Distance traveled by solute (location by the spot)}}{\text{Distance traveled by solvent (Solvent fronts)}}$$

Table 2. Rf values of methanolic extract fractions of *calatropis gigantea* by using thin layer chromatography

S. No.	Fraction	Rf Values
1.	F6	0.1, 0.6, 0.7

2.7. Mass Spectroscopy

The isolated dried crystallized sample are packed in well closed container and sent to National Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (NIPER), Mohali. The mass spectroscopy analysis of ethyl acetate and n-hexane fractions F6 has performed on a Shimadzu lab Solution mass spectrometer system and data were acquired at 02/24/2020.

2.8. Microbial Culture

The four types of most common human bacteria were used in the study: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Bcillus cereus* and *Pseudomonas puteda*. The bacteria were collected from M.T.C.C. Institute of Microbial Technology. We were identifying the selected microorganism by performing their morphological, and physiologically. The bacteria were identified following growth on their selective media and microscopic characteristic [35, 36]. Antimicrobial activity test was performed by disc diffusion method by using guideline of Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) of Microbiology [37].

2.8.1. Antimicrobial Assay of Isolated Compound

Antimicrobial assay of isolated compound of *calatropis gigantea* was performed by disc diffusion method in Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates 16-18. The test organisms were inoculated in Nutrient broth and incubated overnight at 37°C to adjust the turbidity to 0.5 McFarland standards giving a final inoculum of 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml [38]. The test sample was dissolved in water to give the concentration of solution to 200µg/disc, 400µg/disc, 600µg/disc, 800µg/disc and 1000µg/disc and Amoxicillin (30µg/disc) were prepared. The sterile paper discs were placed in known amount of test and standard concentration with the help of transfer loop. Disk of the sample were kept in sterile petridishes (120 mm in diameter) containing microorganism with the help of sterile transfer loop. The plates were then kept in incubator at 25°C for 24 hrs to allow the growth of the microorganisms. Next day clear, distinct zone were obtained of the test agent it determined by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm and this zone of inhibition were compared to the standard antibiotic [39].

2.8.2. Measurement of Zone of inhibition using disc diffusion Method

The MIZ was determined using the Disc diffusion method by the Kirby-Bauer technique and as per recommendation of NCCLS (NCCLS, 1997). The concentrations evaluated were 200, 400, 600, 800, and 1000 µg/mL for isolated compound and on the same concentration 200, 400, 600, 800 and 1000 µg/mL for pure compounds [40].

3. Results

3.1. Identification of major compound

The present study was conducted to prepare polarities crude extract from the flower of *calatropis gigantea*. The highest activity methanolic crude extract was subjected to column chromatography to give three compounds. On the basis Mass spectroscopy the isolated compound was identified as (1) Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid Palmitolieic acid Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid (2) Oxadiazon and (3) only one compound are unknown [41, 42].

3.2. Mass Spectroscopy analysis

The major three compounds of methanolic fraction are identified from both the fraction ethyl acetate and n-hexane as described in experimental section through mass spectroscopy. The identified compounds checked with the available references and the one compound is not found to be reported anywhere from *calatropis gigantea* linn. The active principles with their molecular formula and molecular weight (MW), components present in the ethyl acetate fraction and n-hexane of *Calotropis gigantea* linn flowers have identified by mass spectroscopy analysis (table 3 and Figure 3). The mass spectrums showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 267.10, 340.20 and 289.10 follow a molecular formulas of $C_{17}H_{32}O_2$ (MW 267.10), $C_{15}H_{18}Cl_2N_2O_3$ (MW 340.20), unknown (MW 289.10) have identified three methanolic extract

compounds namely (1) Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid Palmitolieic acid Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid (2) Oxadiazon and only one compound are unknown. The mass spectra of this compound are given in the table -3.

S. No.	Compound	Molecular weight(g/mol)	Fraction	Molecular formula
1.	Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid Palmitolieic acid Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid n-Hexadecanoic acid n-Hexadecanoic acid Tetradecanoic acid	267.10	71.00,80.20,129.80, 212.95	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O ₂
2.	Oxadiazon	340.20	86.05, 95.75, 142.80, 329.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃
3	unknown	289.10	121.05,133.00,139.05, 186.80,	unknown

Fig.3. Mass spectroscopy of isolated compound of calatropis gigantea flower linn.

3.3. Antibacterial assay

In the present investigation, the inhibitory effect of isolates Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid Palmitolieic acid Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid, Oxadiazon and unknown compound of *calatropis gigantea flower* were evaluated against four bacteria (staphylococcus aureus, straptococcus sp, bacillus cereus, Pseudomonas puteda). The antimicrobial activity was determined using agar well diffusion method summarized in Table 4. The activity was quantitatively assessed on the basis of inhibition zone.

3.4. Measurement of Zone of inhibition using disc diffusion Method

The antimicrobial potential of isolates (200 µg/disc, 400 µg/disc, 600 µg/disc 1000µg/disc) was evaluated according to their zone of inhibition against various microorganism and the results (zone of inhibition) were compared with the activity of the standards, viz., Amoxicillin (200 µg/disc, 400 µg/disc, 600 µg/disc 1000µg/disc). The results revealed that all the isolates are potent antimicrobials against all the microorganisms studied. For all the tested microorganisms the isolates activities were maximum in *staphylococcus aureus*. In concentration 1000 µg/ml maximum inhibition zone diameter was obtained in *staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Bacillus cereus* and *pseudomonas puteda* with diameter 24±0.30 mm, 18±0.25 mm, 15±0.40 mm, and 13±0.25 mm respectively. The concentrations of *Staphylococcus aureus* (10±0.00 mm, 12±0.60mm, 16±0.45mm, 18±0.86mm, and 24±0.30mm), *Streptococcus mutans* (7±0.36 mm, 10±0.20 mm, 13±0.85mm, 15±0.46mm, and 18±0.25 mm) and *Bacillus cereus* (2.5±0.0mm, 5.2±0.69 mm, 8±0.50mm, 12±0.75mm, and 15±0.40mm) were showed maximum inhibition zone as compare to *Pseudomonas puteda* (0±0.00 mm, 2.1±0.70 mm, 8.1±0.35mm, 12±0.47mm, and 13±0.25mm). The concentration of *Pseudomonas puteda* was restrained and minimum activity with the minimum inhibition zone. More specifically, *staphylococcus aureus* and *bacillus cereus* represented higher susceptibility to all bacterial strains. The activity of standard compound also show maximum zone of inhibition as compared to another microorganism (Table 4 & Fig.5).

Table 4. Anti-bacterial Activity (Zone of inhibition) of Isolated Compound of *Calatropis gigantea* flower.

S. No.	Test compound (Isolates)	Staphylococcus aureus	Streptococcus mutans	Bacillus cereus	Pseudomonas puteda
	Disk Concentration (µg/ml)	Inhibition Zone (mm)	Inhibition Zone(mm)	Inhibition Zone (mm)	Inhibition Zone (mm)
a)	200	10±0.00	7±0.36	2.5±0.0	0±0.00
b)	400	12±0.60	10±0.20	5.2±0.69	2.1±0.70
c)	600	16±0.45	13±0.85	8±0.50	8.1±0.35
d)	800	18±0.86	15±0.46	12±0.75	12±0.47
e)	1000	24±0.30	18±0.25	15±0.40	13±0.25

Table 5. Anti-bacterial (Zone of inhibition) Activity of Standard Compound (Amoxicillin).

S. No.	Standard compound (Amoxicillin)	Staphylococcus aureus	Streptococcus mutans	Bacillus cereus	Pseudomonas puteda
	Disk Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Inhibition Zone (mm)	Inhibition Zone(mm)	Inhibition Zone (mm)	Inhibition Zone (mm)
a)	200	12 \pm 0.04	8.5 \pm 0.71	4 \pm 0.04	4 \pm 0.44
b)	400	15 \pm 0.21	14 \pm 0.32	6 \pm 0.30	5 \pm 0.69
c)	600	20 \pm 0.30	17 \pm 0.20	9 \pm 0.22	9 \pm 0.90
d)	800	25 \pm 0.20	17 \pm 0.31	10 \pm 0.31	12 \pm 0.33
e)	1000	28 \pm 0.55	20 \pm 0.40	18 \pm 0.40	16 \pm 0.53

Graph A: Zone of inhibition of test compound against various microorganisms.

Graph B: Zone of inhibition of standard compound against various microorganisms.

Fig.4. Zone of inhibition of test compound.

Fig.5. Zone of inhibition of standard compound.

4. Discussion

Currently, drug resistance reported in human and animal pathogens is an important problem in public health, and the use of plants with antimicrobial activity is a potential source of new antibiotics that offer therapeutic benefits and affordable treatments. Despite reports about the antibacterial activity of this plant, the chemical components responsible of these pharmacological effects have not been identified. Table 4 (1-2) shows the Zone of inhibition obtained for Isolated compound in different concentration. The methanolic extract of *Calatropis gigantea* obtained in this study has aslightly antibacterial effect against all tested bacteria. The 1000µg/ml of isolated compound was the most active fraction (S.aureus=17±0.30, S. mutans=15±0.25, B. cereus=18±0.40, L. P. putide=15±0.25). The isolates of calatropis compounds were more active against S. aureus, S. mutans and B. cereus while were restrained and minimum active against P. putide. These results suggested to us that the antibacterial compounds from C. gigantea flower l. were in the organic fraction. Chromatographic purification of methanolic extract of calatropis gigantea allows us identified (1) Cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid or Palmitoleic acid or Z-7-Herxadecenoic acid (2) Oxadiazon and (3) unknown compounds with antibacterial activity. These pharmacological actions have been associated with the capacity of these compounds to form ionic and peptide bonds, thus modulating enzymatic activity, ion channels, transporters and transcription factors.

5. Conclusion

In the present study the compound isolated from the Flower of *Calatropis gigantea L.* showed antibacterial activity against the bacteria. The antibacterial activity was found comparable to that of Amoxicillin, a standard antibiotic. The isolated compound, therefore, may act as antibiotic and take a significant role to fight against multiple antibiotic resistances in bacterial populations in near future. All the findings of the present study warrant further research wherein *Calotropis gigantea* flowers need to be a further experimental analysis, for the evaluation of a potential drug in the treatment of bacterial diseases, but this work proposes the beneficial aspects of medicinal plant.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

Funding

No funding

Author contributions

MV, SPR, and LS designed the study and wrote the manuscript while the SP has interpreted the data. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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